

MEANING OF CULTURE MALAY PALEMBANG LANGUAGE (FROM SYSTEMATIC FUNCTIONAL LINGUISTICS AND SEMANTICS)

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Abstract

Function and use of language as culture is in conveying experiences, understanding and perceptions of life carried out transitively. The aim of this research is to discuss the transitivity of Palembang Malay and Functional Linguistics. The research method uses a mixed method approach. Sources in the form of Palembang Malay language conversations and direct conversational dialogue. Through the Palembang language dialogue stages. The results were that six existing transitivity processes were found based on transitivity stages, namely: (1). The material process stages total 9 clauses, (2). Stages of mental process 6 clauses, (3). Stages of verbal process 4 clauses, (4). Stages of the behavior process 3 clauses, (5). Stages of the existential process 1 clause, (6). Stages of the relational process 1 clause. From the meaning perspective; event and action are 14, cognition and functional meaning are 6, the abstract meaning is 0, and the social-behavioral is 3. Eggins states that the transitivity process of Palembang Malay is apart from actions that go through the process stages that have been directed to the end of the functions and uses that lead to the meaning contained in the conversation. Allan refers more to the series of meanings implied by the Palembang Malay language conversation process compared to the actual process of the verbal form of conversation.

Keywords: Perspective Meaning; SFL; Semantics; Verb Transitivity; Malay Language.

INTRODUCTION

According to: Hasan (2001:25-28). Also explains that the collection of meanings is actually in the form of speech uttered by the speaker, but we cannot ascertain whether the spoken form of meaning can be understood naturally or must be thought of the first speaker, how does the grammatical arrangement he made systematically or not so that there will be no misunderstanding which results in the speaker's intent and purpose to the listener. Then, Kreidler (2002:62) says that the meaning purpose of sentences is simply an idea that is well thought out in the brain so that the spoken sentence will be understood correctly according to the grammar of a particular language. Thus a good sentence is a sentence that is carefully considered whether the meaning contained in the conversation will be easily understood and bring a positive influence on a clear understanding to listeners that have an impact on the smooth communication.

Here are some examples of related research: Dialect Variation Research: Many studies have been conducted to explore dialect variations in various regions in Indonesia. This kind of research discusses differences in word use, spelling and everyday language in various regions. Rahayu., (2018:57). Toponymy (Research on the meaning of place names): This research focuses on the origins of place names in Indonesia and how they describe the history, culture and geography of the area (Erliani, 2021:87). Semantic and Pragmatic Studies: Semantic and

pragmatic research often examines the meaning of words and language structures in various social and cultural contexts in Indonesia (Bawamenewi, 2020; Sawaki, 2023; Silalahi, 2005). Analysis of Meaning in Regional Culture and Literature: This research discusses how meaning in regional culture and literature is reflected in language and literary works (Isnaeni, 2021; Rahmat, 2021; Jazuli, 2023). Historical Linguistics: This research involves reconstructing the history of language and changes in meaning in regional languages over time (Hariyanto, 2016; Khreesda-oh, 2022).

Figure 1: Meaning Perspective

Source: Allan (2001)

There are many studies related to transitivity in text, discourse, teaching, literature, and speech. But there is very little research on regional language dialogue. This study attempts to analyze the transitivity process of the Palembang Malay language verb with the perspective of Systemic Functional Linguistics along with its meaning. Starting from the existence of the research, the researcher wants to know the realization of the transitivity process in Palembang Malay language with the following research questions; Can all transitivity processes be found in the Palembang Malay language conversation dialog?. What kinds of meanings dominate Palembang's Malay language dialogue?

Table 1: Transitivity Process according to Eggins (2004)

No	Process	Meaningful reference
1.	Material	Shows an activity in the form of an action
2.	Mental	The realization of verbs is related to the meaning that is thought or felt
3.	Verbal	The activity process that occurs takes the form of action
4.	Behavioral	Behavior that occurs between mental and material processes.
5.	Existential	The embodiment of experience that shows the existence
6.	Relational	The strategy in the clause how the expression of being can be applied

Next, there is an example of the application of the transitivity process described by Eggins (2004) as follows:

Material Process

A process that shows activity in the form of action. As an example.

Table 2: Examples of Action Forms

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	She	carried	The bomb
2	Actor	Production Materials	Goal

She is referred to as an Actor because it is a participant or subject who performs an active action. The verb carried is a material process in the form of real action. Whereas the word bomb is called a Goal as a direct object.

In addition, the material process has what is called a range that is the expansion of objects and clients that have meaning for whom the work is carried out and the recipient that has meaning for whom it is given.

Mental process

The mental process is an embodiment of verbs related to the meaning that is thought or felt. As an example

Table 3: Mental Manifestation Process

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	She	Believed	his excuses
2	Senser	Prod. Mental. Affection	Phenomenon

In this mental process, there are several types of categories, namely;

- 1) A mental process called perception, for example, she watches football (she watched football). The word she functions as an actor; whereas the word watches as a process of mental perception and noun phrase the football as a phenomenon.
- 2) Mental processes of cognition like I divide a piece of big cake (I divide a large piece of cake). Word I can be identified as an actor, calculate it as a cognitive mental process and the phrase a piece of big cake as a phenomenon.
- 3) The process of mental desideration is a way to express 'desires'

Table 4: Mental Consideration Process

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	I	don't want	any trouble
2	Senser	Prod. mental, desideration	Phenomenon

Verbal Process

The verbal process is a process that occurs in the form of actions and includes verbal symbolic.

As an example:

Table 5: Verbal Processes as Actions

No	Predicate	Material	Objective	No
1	The teacher	Told	Her	a strictly
2	Sayer	Pr. verbal	Receiver	Verbiage

In the table above there is a participant sayer who is responsible for the verbal process. The appearance of a receiver that functions as a receiving object. The appearance of verbiage is a nominalization of information statements from verbal processes. The class behavior of the word 'noun' in this context is an expression of the verb's own behavior.

Behavioral Process

The behavior process is a process that occurs between mental and material processes. As an example:

Table 6: Behavioral Processes as Mental

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	George	Sniffed	the soup.
2	Behavior	Pr. behaviour	Phenomenon

In this example, if there is a participant who is not an advanced statement then the participant is called a phenomenon.

Existential Process

The existential process is an embodiment of experience which shows that "there is" means "there is" that does not refer to an object or place. There serves as a false subject and as a description. The characteristics of the existential process are usually the tobe in the clause. As an example:

Table 7: Characteristics of the Existential Behavior Process

No	Predicate	Material	Objective	No
1	There	Was	snow	on the ground
2		Pr. existential	Existent	Circ. Location

Relational Process

The relational process is a strategy in clauses how the expression of being can be applied. As an example:

Table 8: Relational Strategy Process

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	Diana	is	a talkative dinner guest
2	Carrier	Pr.intensive	Attributive

Other occurrences occur in forms like the illustration below:

Table 9: Illustrative Process Forms

No	Predicate	Material	Objective
1	Her boyfriend's	Was	the bomb
2	Value/possessor	Pr: intensive	Token/possessed

METHOD

The research method uses a mixed method approach (Sugiyona., 2018). The data source was obtained through Palembang Malay language conversations and direct conversation dialogue about monthly family gatherings in the family. The dialogue was then transcribed, recorded and compiled. This research involved 2 respondents.

Data Collection Technique

- a. Through interviews with key respondents who know Malay grammar and culture
- b. Research field observations to observe phenomena that occur in the field
- c. Documentation study to complement previous data, in the form of documentation and Palembang Malay language books.

Data Analysis

Data analysis techniques as a process in studying and processing data related to Malay dangers, relationships, and important information contained therein. The goal is to gain a deeper understanding in Palembang Malay about the data analyzed and make decisions based on the information found

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysis of the meaning of representation in the transitivity process. With the emergence of Palembang verbs as material processes, mental processes, verbal processes, behavioral processes, existential processes, and relationship processes. That Palembang Malay verbals appear in all transitivity processes.

Table 10: Transitivity to the Palembang Malay language dialogue

No	Type	Number
1	Material	9
2	Mental	6
3	Verbal	4
4	Behavioral	3
5	Existential	1
6	Relational	1
Total		25

Material Process

The material process is a verb that occurs meaning an action of the actor called the actor. An example of a conversation dialogue in the following material process is data on the events of conversation dialogue in Palembang Malay.

Table 11: Forms of the Actor's Action Process

No	Perpetrator	Expression	Food
1	Younger brother	shopping	tekwan
2	Younger brother	shopping	tekwan
3	Actor	Proc. Material	Goals

In the Palembang Malay verb clause, the material process above consists of two participants namely actors and goals and verbs with the material process are words (belanja / shopping). So the material process is the actor + proc.material + goal. Thus the verb clause of the Palembang Malay language can appear with the actor + proc pattern. Material + goal.

Mental process

In this process, the participants involved are sensors and phenomena can be seen in the following example

Table 12: Process of Participants Involved

No	Name	Characteristic	Food
1	Mangcik	fierce	Pempek lenggang
2	Mangcik	Want to	Pempek lenggang
3	senser	Proc. Mental. Perception	Phenomenon

It can be found that the Palembang Malay language verb clause also experienced a mental perception process which included two participants namely senser and phenomenon. So that the appearance pattern in the mental process with the + proc senser arrangement. Mental; perception + phenomenon.

Verbal process

Explain the equality of a subject as a sign of a verbal process. Like the following example;

Table 13: Verbal Process Signs

No	Name	Characteristic	Work
1	Wak Cak	begawe	it's all right
2	Bibi Cak	Work	Finish quickly
3	Sayer	Proc. verbal	Cir. of manners

In the Palembang Malay language, a verbal process patterned as sayer + Pr was found. verbal + cir. of manner or sayer + Pr. verbal + Receiver + Verbiage.

Behavioral process

In the behavioral process shows behavioral activities on the material process with mental processes. The behavioral process can be seen in the following example:

Table 14: Examples of Behavioral Processes

No	Name	Characteristic	Mention
1	Fakhri	frowned	Yur money is small change
2	Fakhri	pouting	The money is change'
3	S	V	O
4	Behaver	Pr. Behavioral	Behavior

The transitivity pattern that can be found from the Palembang Malay language is Behaver + Pr. behavioral + behavior.

The Existential Process

The existential process is a process characterized by the words 'there' and 'be'. In the existential process the Malay language of Palembang can be explained as an example:

Table 15: Existential Sign Process

No	Predicate	Food	Market
1	Adonyo	Cork iwak	at the Anyar market
2	There is	Fish cork	at the Anyar market
3		Pro. Existential	Circ. of location

The structure pattern found in the clause is pr. existential + Circ. of location

Relational process

The relational process is a strategy of how expression becomes applied. In the Palembang Malay verb, the verb relational transitivity process with this linguistic functional systemic approach can be explained as follows.

Table 16: Rational Process Strategy

No	Name	Mention	Predicate
	Si Meli	Lah jadi	kayo
	Si meli	menjadi	Orang kaya
	Carrier	Pr. intensive	Attribute

The transitivity pattern of the relational process in Palembang Malay is carrier + Pr. Intensive + attribute. However, when viewed from the four perspectives of the meaning of the category of Allan (2001), only three meaning perspectives are found, namely; The events and actions amounted to 14, functional meaning cognitions numbered 6, no abstract meanings namely 0, and social behaviors totaling 3. There are three dominant perspectives that appear in the transitivity process of the Malay Malay verb are

- a) The meaning of events and actions (event and action) which is a fusion of transitivity from material, verbal and existential processes.
- b) Functional meaning cognition (cognition of functional meaning), is the transitivity of mental process.

- c) The meaning of social behavior (social behavior)), is the transitivity of the behavioral/behavioral process. While the abstract meaning (abstract meaning) is not found in the transitivity of the Palembang Malay verb.

The perspective of the meaning of event and act of language which is a manifestation of a series of events both as an object or subject to an ongoing event can be seen:

- a. Material transitivity processes in Palembang Malay language, namely; In the perspective of the meaning of the Palembang Malay language verb clause, the material process above consists of two participants namely *Adek*/younger sibling as an actor who has the function of the subject/actor and *tekwan* as objects/goals and the meaning of the verb word activity process (*belanja*/shopping). So that it can be understood the meaning of the process of events in the Palembang Malay language there is a subject or object in progress.
- b. the perspective of the meaning of the verbal process of transitivity in the Malay language, namely; meaningful explains the equality of a subject as a sign of a verbal process. As the following example; In the Palembang Malay language, a verbal process was patterned as sayer + Pr. verbal + cir. of manner or sayer + Pr. verbal + Receiver + Verbiage. In the perspective of the meaning of the Palembang Malay language verb clause, the verbal process consists of one participant namely *Wak cak*/aunt Cak meaning as a speaker who has the function of the meaning of the subject and function of the word verbal, while the meaning of the process is manner words (*gancang nian*/fast). So that it can be understood the meaning of the process of verbal events in the ongoing Palembang Malay language.
- c. the perspective of meaning in existential process is a process characterized by the words 'there' and 'be'. In the existential process Palembang Malay language can be explained as an example: In the perspective of the meaning of the Palembang Malay language verb clause, the existential process of structural pattern found in the clause is pr. existential + Circ. of location. So that it can be understood the meaning of the process of the occurrence of events in the ongoing Palembang Malay language.
- d. The functional perspective of cognition (cognition of functional meaning), is the transitivity of the mental process. In this process, the participants involved are senser and the phenomenon can be seen in the following example; It is understandable that the meaning of the Palembang Malay language verb clause also undergoes a mental perception process in which this process belongs to the function of the meaning of cognition which includes two participants namely senser and phenomenon. So that the pattern of emergence in the mental process with the arrangement of the senser (*mangcik* as the perpetrator) + proc. mental; perception (verb i.e. want + phenomenon as an object that is *pempek lenggang*).
- e. The perspective of meaning on social behavior is the transitivity of the behavioral processes that show behavioral activities in material processes with the mental process. The behavioral process can be seen in the following example:

Table 17: Examples of behavioral processes

No	Name	Character	Situation
1	Fakhri	frowned	the money is small change
2	Fakhri	pouting	the money is change'
3	S	V	O
4	Behaver	Pr. Behavioral	Behaviour

The transitivity pattern that can be found from the Palembang Malay language is Behaver meaning a subject acting as a person who behaves + Pr. Behavior is a verb that has the meaning of the results of the action of the subject + a meaningful behavior of the object that gives rise to a process of unhappiness. From the four perspectives of the meaning of Allan's category (2001) on the meaning of the transitivity process of the verbs in Palembang Malay language only found three perspectives of meaning, namely; Events and actions amounted to 14, functional meaning cognition numbered 6, abstract meaning not found, 0, and social behavior found in number 3. There is a very significant correlation finding from the conversational analysis of Palembang Malay language seen from the process of transitivity (Eggin) and based on the perspective of meaning (Allan), namely; *First*, when seen from the action or known material process by Eggin and the process of events and actions according to Allan shows the number of results in the main ranking in the category of verbs that show real action that can be seen from the overall data conversation that is spoken by Malay people in Palembang.

Both Eggin and Allan have a similarity in the position of the mental or cognition sequence in the Palembang Malay language conversation after doing conversation, this explains that action must be taken immediately in overcoming a problem, then along with the ongoing work must be considered to think positively incomplete the work by considering the kindness obtained and overriding the negative results of the action. In addition to the equations that come from the two views of the linguists, there are also some findings that are very significant differences from the process categories according to Eggin and the perspective of meaning according to Allan. *First*, there is a verbal process in Palembang Malay language conversations based on transitivity categories according to Eggin, whereas based on the category of perspective the meaning based on Allan is abstract and this is very contradictory to what has been stated based on the verbal transmission process which is explained based on Eggin's transitivity process.

This oral form is clearly found in Palembang Malay language conversations in the context of family gathering. *Second*, based on the perspective of meaning according to Allan that the conversations found in Palembang Malay language are all abstract in nature which explains that verbal conversations expressed cannot be seen in verbal form and are only seen from the meaning behind the speech. It can be understood that the perspective of meaning seen from the oral form of Palembang Malay language conversation is only in the form of the meaning implied in the spoken conversation. It is clear that Allan's reference to the meaning-focused on the results of thoughts that are abstract in nature but impact on the concrete actions of the results of cognitive language speakers. Third, it can be understood that the category of the emergence of the verbal process from the transitivity process according to Eggin is departing from actions that go through the process stages that have been directed so that towards the end of the

functions and uses that lead to the meaning contained in the conversation. However, on the contrary, Allan refers more to the series of meanings implied by the Palembang Malay language conversation process compared to the actual process of the verbal form of conversation, although it does not rule out the possibility that Allan indirectly accepts the process of real action in the ongoing conversation. Thus, this could be due to the main focus of the category perspective proposed by Allan is to rotate in the realm of meaning. Therefore Allan only categorizes four perspectives that are very important in every conversation that exists in the Malay language of Palembang. The dominating process of transitivity is found in many material processes if it is associated with the behavior and social aspects of the Palembang community it could be that in general the actions of the cultural behavior of Palembang people act directly and decisively not long-winded and stale in conveying messages in the form of direct and indirect. It can be clearly seen that there is little emergence in relational and existential processes, this is related to the general attitude and character of Palembang Malay people who do not make predictions about statements that may not be certain. This research is also in line with (Sujatna 2012) about the research on the transitivity of Sundanese verbs, but the research conducted by Sujatna is only limited to one angle of analysis of perceptual mental transitivity processes and does not analyze the six processes proposed by Edgins (2004).

The research on the transitivity of the Palembang Malay verb is also in harmony with (Nguyen 2012) which examines the conversation dialogue of the main actors on the heroic mother film in Vietnam. Nguyen examined the six transitivity processes based on the Halliday theory. All transitivity processes arise. See, (Ignatieva 2014) her research about the "verbal process in academic writing. In her research results of the analysis, there many variations of the verbal process in different genres and areas with unnatural language. However, the differences in the analysis that are significant in language data that are of an unnatural nature are based on conversational dialogues that have been designed and thought out according to the purpose of making the film. Whereas the transitivity process of the Palembang Malay language is based on natural data from direct language speakers. It is very different from the two studies of transitivity processes, both Sujatna and Nguyen that they only examine the occurrence of transitivity processes, while the Palembang Malay language research not only examines the verb transitivity process but analyzes the perspective of meaning that occurs in every transitivity process.

CONCLUSION

This study explores two problems, namely the emergence of all verb transitivity processes in the Palembang Malay language dialogue and the perspective of many and few meanings that emerge in the Palembang Malay dialogue. This study found 6 types of transitivity processes. The six transitivity processes that arise are: (First) material processes totaling 9 clauses, (Second) mental processes 6 clauses, (third) verbal processes 4 clauses, (fourth) behavioral processes 3 clauses, (fifth) existent 2 clausal processes, (sixth) relational process 1 clause. While from the four perspectives the meaning of the category only found three perspectives of meaning, namely; the events and actions amounted to 14, functional meaning cognition numbered 6, no abstract meanings namely 0, and social behaviors totaling 3.

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